
Motivating Student Engagement

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SUMMARY

Existing Knowledge:

1. Motivation is vital for fostering interest and participation in learning, directly impacting academic success.
2. Classroom participation enhances critical thinking, interpersonal skills, and democratic collaboration.
3. Challenges to engagement include personal traits, classroom dynamics, and insufficient motivational strategies.

New Insights:

1. Students' lack of interest stems from distractions, difficult lessons, and inadequate teacher-student interaction.
2. Teachers face time constraints, struggle with instructional materials, and encounter challenges aligning strategies with students' needs.
3. Reward systems, engaging activities, and fostering positive environments can significantly enhance student motivation.

Putting Research into Practice:

1. Implement student-centered approaches, emphasizing relevance and interactive learning.
2. Use visual aids, rewards, and communication techniques to increase participation and focus.
3. Train teachers in creating inclusive, supportive environments to address individual student needs effectively.

Keywords:

motivation, engagement, participation, teaching strategies, classroom environment, learning outcomes

Reference:

Rone, N. A., Guao, N. A. A., Jariol, M. S., Jr., Acedillo, N. B., Balinton, K. R., & Francisco, J. O. (2023). Students' lack of interest, motivation in learning, and classroom participation: How to motivate them? *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 7, 636-645.
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